

DEVELOPMENT OF SELF HEALING RESIN MATRICES FOR COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

An ideal self-healing matrix composite which is capable of being monitored for damage events in the matrix so that they can be healed in a thermal cycle to restore the material's performance without negatively affecting the properties is discussed. A novel technique employing a solid-state matrix repair system for a thermosetting resin that has been shown to be capable of healing of its pre-fracture strength. This paper will describe the concept of a solid-state healable system and its efficiency. In an attempt to optimise the system for processing into composites, the effects of linear polymer with different molecular weight, physical ageing and phase separation have been studied.

Keywords: self-healing, healing process, physical ageing

1. INTRODUCTION

A thermally self-healing epoxy resin, which consists of a linear polymer dissolved in a thermosetting matrix of similar solubility parameter which diffuses to a crack for closure and healing upon heating at a specific temperature has been reported elsewhere [1, 2]. The original linear healing agent had an average molecular weight of 44,000 g/mol which provided an epoxy resin matrix with a healing efficiency of approximately 60% [2]. The healing efficiency was determined by recording the recovery in fracture toughness as measured by the critical strain energy release rate (G_{1c}) and the critical stress intensity factor (K_{1c}) using a compact tension specimen.

The main disadvantage of this system was the high viscosity of modified resin containing the healing agent (HA). In this study we have varied the molecular weight of the linear polymeric healing agent and assessed the healing efficiency in order to demonstrate the mechanism of healing and identify the contribution of hydrogen bonding and the polymer entanglement length. The project employed diglycidyl ethers of differing molecular weight which had been end-capped to remove any potential for reaction of the healing agent with the thermosetting matrix of similar solubility parameter. Therefore, the relationship between the molecular chain length of the healing agent and the time to heal has been studied.

The phase separation of the healing agent has also been studied to explain the reduction in healing efficiency. Phase separation of the healing agent can be observed at high concentrations, which explains the reduction in healing efficiency [1]. The reduction in healing efficiency after multiple cycles has been hypothesized to arise from physical aging in the matrix [3] and/or phase separation of the healing agent, once the actual

mechanisms of healing are defined optimum matrices can be designed. Furthermore, since transverse cracking is the main first ply-failure in a composite laminate and which propagate in either the matrix or the matrix rich interphase region of the material, self repair is a practical reality. We have demonstrated in previous reports that the self healing of damage can be thermally induced in these composites.

This paper present a study to quantify the relationship between the molecular chain length of healing agent (HA) and the kinetics of healing with the ability of the HA to diffuse in epoxy resin and also to verify that effect of physical ageing with the reduction in “free volume” and /or phase separation maybe responsible for a reduction in self healing efficiency.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and Sample Preparation

The neat epoxy resin (ER) prepared for this study was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (Epikote 828) that cured with nadic methylene tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (NMA) and benzyl dimethyl amine (BDMA) as an accelerator. The formulation is given in Table 1. Poly(Bisphenol-A-co-epichlorohydrin) or (PDGEBA) from Sigma Aldrich with average Mw of 44 000 g/mol was use as an effective healing agent in previous study [1]. Meanwhile, PDGEBA, glycdyl end-capped (PDGEBAC) with average Mw of 6100 g/mol or 4000 g/mol need to react with benzoic acid in the melt blending process in order to deactivate the epoxy group and remain non-reactive to thermoset system.

The healing agent (HA) was dissolved in Epikote 828 at 80°C under stirring over several hours until there was no evidence of the undissolved thermoplastic and degassed at 50°C. The remaining ingredients were blended in at 80°C before further degassed. The mixture was finally poured into a mould before curing in the oven at 90 °C for 5 h and post-curing at 150 for 2 h. The unmodified epoxy resin (ER) was also made with the same curing condition as above.

Table 1: Formulation for epoxy resin.

Ingredient	Component	Chemical equivalent (phr)
Resin matrix	Epikote 828	100
Hardener	NMA	81.2
Catalyst	BDMA	2

2.2. Assessment of Healing

Testing of the ability of the matrix to heal was carried out using compact tension (CT) testing, with samples being prepared according to BS13586:2000 [4] as shown in Figure 1. The crack was arrested before the specimen fully fractured under tension by introducing a hole in the plane of the crack, as shown below. The specimen was loaded under displacement control using a Tensile Testing Machine Type T5002 with a displacement rate of 10mm/min and a load capacity of 20 N.

Figure 1: Illustration and dimensions of the compact tension test specimens.

2.3. Deactivation of The Epoxy Group

Fourier-transform infrared spectrometer (FTIR) measurement was made with a Perkin-Elmer, S2000. A small number of shavings of the samples of sample were mixed with potassium bromide (KBr) technique (1:100 mg) and ground into fine powder before further pressed into thin discs for FTIR measurement. All spectra are record at room temperature and signal-average over 64 scans at a resolution 2 cm^{-1} and 1 cm^{-1} interval, in the infrared spectra range $4000\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

2.4 Dynamic Mechanical Analyst and Volume Measurement

The dynamic mechanical properties of the samples were determined using a dynamic mechanical thermal analyzer (DMTA) by PerkinElmer. The samples with dimension of approximately $30\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm} \times 1\text{ mm}$ were loaded horizontally in DMTA standard medium size clamps. Measurements were performed in the dual cantilever-bending mode. The spectra were collected from -135°C to 180°C at a heating rate of $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and a frequency of 1.0 Hz .

Meanwhile, the room temperature density of both the annealed samples and reference (quenched) samples was measured using density balance in a density gradient column based on water solutions using Archimedes Principle. This technique required that the mass of the compact be measured before and after it was saturated with a solvent (water, in this case) and while it was suspended in the solvent.

2.5 Resin Morphology

Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) was carried out on a Bruker AXS solid-state detector at room temperature with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda=1.541\text{ \AA}$). The sample-to-detector distances were 1 m . The scattered beam intensity was plotted as a function of the variable q , which is defined as $q = 2(\sin \theta)/\lambda$, where θ is the scattered angle and λ is the wave-length of the X rays (X-ray wavelength (0.15 nm)).

Meanwhile, optical images were registered using a Reichert-Jung POLYVAR MET light optical microscope, attached to a CCD Color Camera model KC-512NTX (KODO

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Deactivation of Glycidyl Ether in PDGEBAC

The end-capping of PDGEBAC as above to deactivate the epoxy group was achieved by reaction with benzoic acid. The extent of reaction was confirmed by infrared spectroscopy as shown in Figure 2. This involves the transformation of carboxylic acid groups from benzoic acid into ester groups after the interaction with PDGEBAC. In Figure 2a, the IR spectrum of benzoic acid shows a carbonyl band at 1713 cm^{-1} . The spectrum of PDGEBAC-Benzoic acid reaction product exhibits an ester band at 1726 cm^{-1} as shown in Figure 2c while there is no absorption peak within this range that can be detected in PDGEBAC (Fig. 2b).

Moreover, the opening of the epoxy ring was expected to reduce the intensity with absorption band at 910 cm^{-1} (Fig. 2b). As shown in Figure 2c, after reaction in the melt the intensity of the band at 910 cm^{-1} is reduced confirming that the end-capping had occurred.

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of a) Benzoic acid b) PDGEBAC c) PDGEBAC/Benzoic acid blend.

3.2 The Mechanism and Healing Efficiency

The efficiency of the recovery of fracture toughness was calculated for the relative loads required for the crack to propagate through the compact tension specimen as shown in equation 1.

$$R_E = \frac{100 \cdot E_{\text{healed}}}{E_{\text{initial}}} \quad (1)$$

Where E_{healed} and E_{initial} are the post-healing and initial load energies, respectively. R_E is the percentage recovery in load for crack propagation.

The data for three healing cycles are shown to reveal the effect of multiple healing events on the healing performance. Figure 3 shows the percentage recovery of HA/ER blend with average Mw of 44k and 6100 g/mol of HA across the range of time for healing from load to failure data. In the healing cycle process, the increase in the time for healing will provide the degree of recovery at different rate. The kinetic rate of healing with high molecular weight is lower than that with low molecular weight HA indicating of a diffusion mechanism via reptation of the linear polymer to bridge the crack for healing of the cross linked of epoxy resin. Reducing the time for healing can improve the efficiency of recovery especially in the second and third healing cycle because of a lower reduction in a free volume associated with the vascular network of unoccupied volume in the epoxy resin. Diffusion of low molecular weight polymer is faster leading to more rapid healing.

Figure 3: The percentage recovery of fraction in recovery of fracture toughness from CT Test at different times for healing in modified resin system with 7.5wt% of HA with average Mw of a) 44 000 b) 6100 g/mol. *ER was cured at 6 h samples were healed at 130 °C.

Figure 3 also shows that unmodified epoxy resin exhibited a limited self healing ability at the healing temperature because of continued cure (even though the healing temperature is below the cure temperature) and /or relaxation of the polymer network. It is also possible for diffusion of long network chain ends to contribute to healing. To compensate for this, the resin “Healing efficiency” (H_E) has been corrected and re-estimated from Equation 1. Thus, H_E contribution to healing from the addition of the healing agent can be examined.

$$H_E = R_E - R_E^0 \quad (2)$$

Figure 4: DMTA scan of Tan δ for ER with unaged and ageing sample in healing process (130 °C for 6h) between temperature range of a) 100 to 180 °C b) -130 to 0 °C.

Table 2: Corrected healing efficiency (H_E) from Compact tension test as a function of the healing agent molecular weight over several cycles.

Healing agent with different average Mw in ER	Concentration of healing agent (%)	Healing (%)								
		R_E^0			R_E			H_E		
		Healing cycle								
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd
Standard ER without HA	0	9.2	5.1	3.6	—	—	—	—	—	—
	5	—	—	—	40.8	26.0	18.6	31.6	20.9	15.0
44 000 g/mol	7.5	—	—	—	51.8	37.4	28.4	42.6	32.3	24.8
	10	—	—	—	26.6	15.1	12.2	17.4	10.1	8.6
	5	—	—	—	31.8	23.5	14.9	22.6	18.4	11.3
6100 g/mol	7.5	—	—	—	41.4	30.8	22.9	32.2	25.7	19.3
	10	—	—	—	23.8	14.4	10.7	14.6	9.3	7.1
	7.5	—	—	—	39.1	28.6	22.4	29.9	23.5	18.8

3.3 Reduction in Healing Efficiency

The reduction in healing efficiency after multiple cycles has been hypothesized to arise from physical aging in the matrix and/or phase separation of the healing agent at higher loading. The DMA is essentially able to detect all changes in the state of molecular motion in a viscoelastic solid as temperature is scanned. In the glass transition region, the $\tan\delta$ peak value decreased with the aging time and Shifts to higher temperatures [5, 6]. The dynamic mechanical relaxation behavior of standard ER (BDMA/NMA/BDMA) annealed or heal at 130°C during certain time and unaged have been studied. Figure 4 shows of the unaged and aged sample scan shows peaks in the $\tan\delta$ trace at a temperature peak around 134 °C and -90°C corresponding to the glass transition, T_g and secondary peak of broad β -relaxation, T_β . This DMA study has shows that the magnitude of relaxation being depressed upon aging treatment. It is apparent that aging caused chain stiffening, which expectedly resulted in a higher modulus for sample aged with repeated healing cycle. In addition, this result can be attributed to stiffening of the polymer chains in approaching the equilibrium glassy state with reduced free volume and the decrease of the height of the loss factor can be explained by a relaxation in which the epoxy network loses mobility and free volume during its approach toward the equilibrium glassy state and, as a result, the ability to dissipate energy is reduced.

The gradual rearrangement of molecular chains that occurs following a quench from above T_g , causes a gradual increase in density towards the equilibrium value [5]. When the sample is annealed or arrested near T_g , it will have excess thermodynamic quantities (volume) and reduce gradually moves towards the equilibrium state. The internal structure relaxes as a result of a change in the chain conformation by molecular motions that relate with the occupied volume. The occupied volume is the volume occupied by molecular chains and the free volume is the space which permits movement of molecular chains. Consequently, in the free volume framework and the mobility of the chain segments, its decreases the sample volume slowly and continuously to reduce of healing efficiency as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The reduction in volume of unmodified ER with the healing for 6 hours for every cycle at a) room temperature or 25 °C b) 130 °C.

The sudden reduction in healability above 7.5 wt% of HA in ER has been reported elsewhere [1]. Figure 6 shows the SAXS profiles of the modified ER with different wt% of HA. No clearly defined scattering peaks were observed in 0, 5 and 7.5 wt% of HA, indicating that phase separation has not occurred so that the system is considered homogeneous. In contrast, a scattering peak appeared in a sample with 10 wt% of HA in ER blend indicating that difference in average electron density from the interface between the two phases due to the formation of a microphase. According to the position of the primary scattering peaks, the average distance ($L = 2\pi/q_m$) between neighbouring domains can be estimated to be 24.1 nm for the ER containing the HA of 10 wt %, respectively.

Figure 6: SAXS profiles of the cured HA modified epoxy resin as a function of HA concentration showing presence of a scattering peak above 7.5%.

4.5 Morphology Analyst

Characteristic optical micrographs of modified resin sample from CT test before and after healing process are shown in Figure 7. The microcrack line on the sample after fracture can be seen in 0.25X magnification multiplier and clearly detect especially at 20X magnification. After the healing process, this microcrack will be fill and reinforce with the healing agent upon diffusion via a reptation mechanism. In the healing sample at magnification of 0.25X, it difficult to see the microcrack except the contrast dark line

across the sample or along the crack line. However at 20X magnification, it is clearly seen that the crack have been filled and the two fracture surfaces are brought into intimate contact.

Figure 7: Optical microscopic image of modified resin sample from a Compact Tension Test specimen before and after healing.

4. CONCLUSION

There is a relationship between the molecular chain length of HA and the kinetics of healing where the healing is slower with the higher molecular weight HA indicative of a reptation mechanism in the cross linked epoxy resin. These linear healing agents can diffuse through the crosslinked network to the free surface at the crack face. Using longer healing cycles increases the probability that the network relaxes reducing the available free /unoccupied volume for reptation. These phenomena can be clearly seen after second and third healing cycles. The reduction in healing efficiency especially at higher loading of HA may due to the separation of the healing agent as the network relaxes and /or experiences additional crosslinking.

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